

IMPROVING LIABILITY AND LOAN ACCOUNTING IN PRODUCTION BUSINESS UNITS

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Annotation. This article discusses the issues of accounting for liabilities at manufacturing enterprises and their improvement based on international standards. Based on the results of the study, based on financial analysis, scientific proposals and practical recommendations were developed.

Keywords: liabilities, specific liabilities, indefinite liabilities, current liabilities, long-term liabilities, accounts payable, transformation of liabilities.

When we analyze the international legal documents, according to the international accounting standard No. 37 (IAS 37) «Estimated liabilities, contingent liabilities and contingent assets», a liability is an existing responsibility of the organization arising from past events, and as a result of its extinguishment, the economic value of the organization itself It is stated that the outflow of embodied resources is expected [1].

According to the author's definition of the economist A. Kozimjonov, a liability is a responsibility that has arisen as a result of the past and current activities of an economic entity. When grain storage and processing enterprises organize the account of liabilities during financial and management activities according to

international standards of financial reporting, it is appropriate to divide liabilities into the following 4 groups.

1. Liabilities to shareholders and founders.
2. Liabilities to state tax authorities and trust funds.
3. Liabilities to individuals.
4. Liabilities to legal entities [2].

Professor S. Tashnazarov draws attention to the issues that need to be improved in terms of liabilities and writes: «The structure of the current liabilities does not allow the transformation of the statement of financial results into a statement of cash flows. We think that the liabilities arising on the basis of 20-30 transactions issued on the basis of the 6990 «Other liabilities» account in BHMS No. 21 should be reclassified in a form consistent with the composition of expenses and financial results [3].

F. Ochilov, who conducted research in the field of accounting of liabilities, proposed to divide them into clear and uncertain liabilities based on international experience from the point of view of assessment of liabilities. The exact value of specific liabilities is determined in accounting. In particular, liabilities known as debts in the company are directly related to the company's planned financing strategy. Contingent liabilities are liabilities that may arise in the future as a result of operational activities and are estimated abstractly in accounting [4].

Summarizing the above international standard requirements and scientific research of economists, it is possible to conclude that liabilities are an economic category, which includes the concept of debts. In our opinion, it would be logical to include receivables in the composition of liabilities. This is because accounts receivable are also liabilities of the enterprise. Since these debts are not in economic circulation, we believe that it is not logical to take them into account as part of current assets.

The analysis of liabilities based on the elements of formation provides an opportunity to determine their weight, dynamics, as well as optimal management of

economic processes. For this purpose, we will carry out an analysis of liabilities on the example of a pulp and paper production enterprise (Table 1). According to the analysis, it has been proven that the separation of liabilities into two main groups is theoretically and practically acceptable. They consist of elements such as long-term liabilities, current liabilities, including current payables. Current liabilities have a significant weight in the composition of these items, in particular, the current part of creditors has a significant impact on the economic process.

Table 1. Analysis of the dynamics of liabilities by their components [5], in thousand soms

№	Indicators	As of January 1, 2017.	As of January 1, 2018	As of January 1, 2019	As of January 1, 2020	Change, in 2020 compared to 2017, %
1.	Long-term liabilities	206 412,2	195 979,4	218 673,9	230 492,2	111,7
2.	Current liabilities	23 487,7	33 761,9	13 136,3	34 089,4	145,1
3.	including current accounts payable	7 897,2	17 749,9	13 136,3	34 089,4	More than 4 times
4.	Total liabilities	229 899,9	229 741,3	231 810,2	264 581,7	115,1

Source. Author's calculation based on the 2020 financial report of the foreign enterprise «Global Komsco Daewoo» LLC.

The table shows that the total liabilities of the studied facility as of January 1, 2017 are 229,899.9 million soms; 229,741.3 million soms in 2018, respectively; In 2019 it was 231,810.2 million soums and in 2020 it was 264,581.7 million soums.

It should be noted that long-term liabilities increased by 111.7% in 2020 compared to 2017, and current liabilities increased by 145.1%, including the fact that current payables increased by more than 4 times, which had a negative impact on the company's financial condition and stability.

We will analyze the reflection of liabilities in the consolidated report on the financial status of an economic entity on the example of a specific enterprise (Table 2).

Based on the analysis of table data, it should be noted that the financial report of «Navoiyazot» JSC is prepared based on international standards. It takes into account the requirements of international financial reporting standards (IFRS). In particular, on the basis of the standard «First-time application of international standards of financial reporting» MXCC No. 1, as of January 1, 2019 and December 31 of this year, and also as of December 31, 2020, an opportunity arises to make management decisions as a result of comparing the liability section of the company's balance sheet.

Table 2. Reflecting liabilities in the consolidated statement of financial position [6], in million soums

	December 31, 2020	December 31, 2019	January 1, 2019
Liabilities			
Loans and debts	12 006 394	12 871 885	11 731 229
Other long-term liabilities	57 329	45 947	13 653
Deferred tax liabilities	963	1 002	1 040
Long-term liabilities	12 064 686	12 918 834	11 745 922

Loans and debts	3 087 561	722 014	254 662
Trade and other payables	1 460 544	998 666	604 776
Other taxes payable	204 620	7 408	12 462
Current tax liabilities	4 342	1 914	1 765
Current liabilities	4 757 067	1 730 002	873 665
Total liabilities	16 821 753	14 648 836	12 619 587

Source. The author's calculation based on the financial report of «Navoiyazot» JSC.

In conclusion, it is an urgent issue to organize accounting of liabilities in production enterprises based on international standards of financial reporting. Such a demand is appropriate for us to recognize the need not only to transform the national accounting and reporting system to international standards, but also to jointly improve its scientific-theoretical and organizational-methodical foundations.

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